

Dangerous identities in the context of neoliberal globalization

Jesús Guanche¹

*Truth is strengthened by research and delay;
falsehood, by haste and uncertainty.*
Tacit.

Theory is sooner or later killed by experience.
Albert Einstein.

The worldwide implementation of policies and actions of flattening, neutralization or, if possible, disappearance of cultural diversity, permanently endangers identities and their sense of belonging/difference to certain cultural contexts.² This has given rise to fashionable theoretical interpretations that, directly or indirectly, make a pass at neoliberalism and, far from turning it into forceful critiques and alternatives for new proposals of deep economic-social and historical transformation, they become apologists of the system that obviously welcomes and supports them, although it also subjects them to criticism. Such is the case of the work of Néstor García Canclini³ in his interpretation of Latin American complexity reduced to "cultural hybridity" and "consumption" to reach the category of citizens.

One of several critical reflections is made by Misha Kokotovic, from the University of San Diego, California, who points out the scope and limitations of this author's conception. On the one hand, he recognizes that:

Latin America is beginning to be recognized in the English-speaking North American academy not only as an object of study but also as a place of theoretical production. Of the Latin American cultural theorists [...], perhaps the most influential in the current North American intellectual sphere is Néstor García Canclini. His major works have been translated into English and have a wide circulation (not limited to Spanish departments) in the North American academy, while panels have been devoted to him

¹ Anthropologist, Emeritus Academician of the Sciences Academy of Cuba, Full Member of the History Academy of Cuba, and Vice Rector of the Hebei International Studies University, People's Republic of China.

² There can be many examples of the flattening associated with banality as an existential paradigm; for example, through fashion and the mass media that suggest through personal icons (celebrities), groups (artists, athletes and others), news, serials, soap operas, propaganda and participation programs, the use of tattoos and body art, piercings, ripped clothes, junk food, trash TV, multiple addictions, vulgar music, among others; forms of behavior that reduce the human being to the here and now, an attitude that makes it possible for others to think the future for them.

³ Argentine anthropologist based in Mexico as professor and researcher at the Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana Unidad Iztapalapa.

in recent congresses of the American Anthropological Association and the Modern Language Association.⁴

On the other hand, he also warns of the danger of limiting it to a single person, as has occurred with the work of Claude Lévy Strauss (1908-2009) in the United States with respect to other French thinkers in anthropology. For this he exemplifies with the texts if we see it in chronological order of the Cuban Fernando Ortiz (1888-1969) about *transculturation* as a process of permanent change, later developed in literature by the Uruguayan Angel Rama (1926-1983) and the Peruvian Antonio Cornejo Polar (1937-1997) on the conception of *heterogeneity and contradictory totality*, "who capture better and more explicitly [than García Canclini] the inequalities and asymmetrical power relations, even colonial, that condition cultural changes under the current neoliberal phase of capitalist expansion, called globalization".⁵

In Cornejo Polar's own critique of García Canclini's work, he also considers that the "theory of hybridity" is not merely cultural, since it is immersed in history, but with a limited classist vision, since his examples tend to "refer preferentially to certain strata [the upper strata] of Latin American society"⁶ and not to its totality. Generally, in his examples he refers more to Mexico and other South American countries such as Argentina and Chile, than to other Central American⁷ and Caribbean⁸ contexts. In this sense, says Kokotovic:

García Canclini underestimates the growing inequality of Latin American societies. Not all practice hybridity to the same degree or with the same freedom. And as much as García Canclini insists on the conflictive nature of the concept, hybridity suggests, on the contrary, a harmonious, almost natural, combination of diverse cultural elements, and thus lends itself, at least in the North American academy, to an official multiculturalism carefully purged of references to conflicts of material interests.

The exclusionary implications of multiculturalism in the United States and its way of defending WASP status in the face of migratory, cultural, and linguistic diversity are well known.

In contrast with the notion of *hybridity*, the concept of *transculturation*, proposed and highly developed by Fernando Ortiz, is not limited, as Kokotovic believes, to the *Cuban Counterpoint of Tobacco and Sugar* (1940),⁹ where he makes it known, but there are

⁴ See Misha Kokotovic. «Hibridez y desigualdad: García Canclini ante el neoliberalismo», in *Revista de Crítica Literaria Latinoamericana*, Año XXVI, N° 52. Lima-Hanover, 2do. Semestre, 2000: 289-290.

⁵ *Ibidem*: 290.

⁶ See Antonio Cornejo Polar. *Mestizaje e hibridez: los riesgos de las metáforas*. *Revista Iberoamericana*, 180. Universidad Mayor de San Andrés, La Paz, 1997: 342.

⁷ In Central America, the theoretical work of Guatemalan Celso Lara (1958-), who for decades directed the magazine *Folklore Americano*, is unknown or overlooked.

⁸ In the case of the Caribbean, it overlooks or ignores, among other theoretical proposals, the works of the Cubans Antonio Benítez Rojo (1931-2005), Roberto Fernández Retamar (1930-2019) and the Martinican Édouard Glissant (1928-2011), as examples.

⁹ Remember that this is the work of Fernando Ortiz translated into English and the rest of his vast scientific production is still pending.

important later works. Ortiz evidences the processes of transculturation in *El engaño de las razas* [*The deception of the races*](1945), *La africanía de la música folklórica de Cuba* [*The africaness of Cuba's folkloric music*](1950), *Los bailes y el teatro de los negros en el folklore de Cuba* [*Black dances and theater in Cuban folklore*] (1951) and *Los instrumentos de la música afrocubana* [*The instruments of Afro-Cuban music*](1952-1955), together with hundreds of articles, conferences, foundation of associations and publications.¹⁰ That makes him overcome his conceptions of youth, reject the notion of "race", value the role of the arts and its transformations, appropriate in another moment of the *mulatez*¹¹ as permanent cultural mixture and later assume the distinction between "cubanidad and cubanía",¹² to place in the national debate what Miguel de Unamuno (1864-1936) had already differentiated between "hispanidad and hispanía".

The works of Ortiz in the social sciences, especially in the field of the African legacy in the Americas and the Caribbean,¹³ and then of Rama in literature, are based on asymmetrical power relations that characterize colonial and neocolonial cultural legacies and their liberating overcoming; the *heterogeneity* proposed by Cornejo Polar is also based on the study of inequalities and social divisions in Latin America.

These three complementary concepts of heterogeneity, contradictory totality, and transculturation point to the need for self-organization of subaltern groups based on their cultural identities and material interests to collectively confront inequality and subordination. This] is not the case of *hybridity*,¹⁴ which, in addition to its limitations at the descriptive level, also does not function as a normative concept or political strategy, as García Canclini claims.¹⁵

The work of this author has been focused on several areas of attention. In *Las culturas populares en el capitalismo* (1982), he deals with cultural production, inequality, and conflict between hegemonic and subaltern groups; in *Culturas híbridas. Estrategias para entrar y salir de la modernidad* (1990),¹⁶ he tries to dialogue with postmodern theories and deals more with cultural mixtures than with social conflicts; In *Consumidores y ciudadanos* (1995), he evades interest in cultural production and collective social struggles to propose nothing less than the market as the new space for political participation and consumption as the new way of exercising citizenship; and in *Globalización imaginada* (1999), in the same

¹⁰ See Jesús Guanche. "Avatares de la transculturación ortiziana", in *Temas*, Nueva época, Havana, no. 4, October-December 1995: 121-128.

¹¹ See Fernando Ortiz. *Epifanía de la mulatez. Historia y poesía*, Havana, 2015.

¹² See Fernando Ortiz. «Los factores humanos de la cubanidad», in *Fernando Ortiz y la cubanidad*, Havana, 1996.

¹³ For this reason, the International Colloquium 100 Years of Afro-American Studies. Evaluation y Prospective was dedicated to him in 2005, by the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Tepoztlán, Morelos, Mexico, from November 7 to 10.

¹⁴ Italics mine, JG.

¹⁵ Kokotovic, *Op. cit.* :291.

¹⁶ During the first reading of this work, another parodic title implicit in the content jumped out at me: *Drunken Cultures. Strategies to crawl with pessimism and not get out of neoliberalism*.

reductionist line, he restricts a field as complex as global interconnection to metaphors and their narratives. In this sense, the author himself declares that:

[...] we lack a consensual theory on globalization that encompasses the economic, socio-political, cultural dimensions that constitute it. There is nothing at this time to suggest that such a theory will be formed soon. Perhaps what brings us closest to a broad and more encompassing conceptualization of globalization is the linking of some socioeconomic studies with cultural studies and, above all, studies on interculturality.¹⁷

Everything indicates, or at least there are no references, that it also overlooks the broad theoretical work of Immanuel Wallerstein, who evaluates in its complexity what he calls the *world-system*. Unlike García Canclini and his sometimes conformist and sometimes apologist vision of neoliberal globalization, Wallerstein's critique of global capitalism and his influence on anti-system movements have made him an obligatory source of anti-globalization along with other intellectuals such as Noam Chomsky and Pierre Bourdieu. Perhaps that is why it is not surprising that I have not consulted him.

Faced with the dilemma of "Globalize or defend identity: how to get out of this option" ¹⁸ the author, consistent with his thinking, opts for the inevitable neoliberal globalization; so that here too identities are superfluous.

In his analyses, García Canclini still uses the sterile subdivision, long outdated, between "the cultured and the popular", as if there were an impassable frontier between elite or professional expressions, many of which are nourished by popular traditions, and the traditional manifestations of the most disadvantaged sectors. Cultural studies have shown that both are "cultured" in the sense of the continuity of knowledge and know-how, even when learning procedures and areas of family, local, national, or international influence change.¹⁹ The point is not to look down on popular expressions to evaluate them from the academic vantage point.

However, for García Canclini, having a global vision is more important than at any other time because "in this time of postmodern dissemination and democratizing decentralization, the most concentrated forms of accumulation of power and transnational centralization of culture that humanity has ever known are also growing".²⁰

¹⁷ See Juan de la Haba y Enrique Santamaría. «Entrevista a Néstor García Canclini. Dilemas de la globalización: hibridación cultural, comunicación y política», in *Voces y culturas. Revista de Comunicación*, no. 17, Barcelona, 2001: 143-165.

¹⁸ See Claudia Pedone y Alejandro Goldberg. *GARCÍA CANCLINI, Néstor. La globalización imaginada*, en https://www.researchgate.net/publication/39087379_GARCIA_CANCLINI_Nestor_La_globalizacion_imaginada (Consultado el 16 de noviembre de 2018).

¹⁹ UNESCO's own effort to apply and declare the results of the 2003 Convention on cultural heritage identified as "intangible" or supposedly "immaterial" is a very commendable example of highlighting the values, knowledge and know-how of expressions rooted worldwide.

²⁰ See *Culturas híbridas: estrategias para entrar y salir de la modernidad*. 1990:25.

Postmodern disquisitions on cultural differences do not take into consideration structural inequality and are therefore useless to explain the concentration of economic and political power brought about by the neoliberal restructuring of transnational capitalism.²¹ However, for García Canclini, to renounce a global perspective is to resign oneself to the growing inequality of neoliberalism. But "García Canclini's main theoretical concept, *cultural hybridity*,²² conceals more than it reveals of the concentration of power and centralization of culture that García Canclini so aptly identifies as the counterpart of postmodern dissemination".²³

That is why it makes a precocious generalization of hybridization for processes carried out only by the social sectors of domination and not in the whole of society, due to the growing tendency towards inequality, also increased by neoliberalism, where the minority rich are getting richer and the majority poor are getting poorer; the less favored sectors do not have the opportunity to freely combine cultural elements when their main vision is reduced to the struggle for subsistence.

This is precisely the situation on which the movement of the indignant *Occupy Wall Street* is based, which operationally indicates that most of the population (99%) is disadvantaged by the abyss of inequality, in the face of the smallest richest part, according to some 1%, according to others 0.1% and for others 0.0000063%. It is this minority that makes economic, political, and social decisions of global scope against the interests of the majority. In this sense:

Economic and financial power is based on the power of individuals who derive their power from the ownership they have over financial and corporate capital. This clarification is necessary because financial institutions and large companies are controlled by flesh and blood people who have their own names and surnames and whose number is much smaller than the population believes. Today we are governed financially and economically by very minority elites, who are behind those institutions and who have enormous influence over the institutions defined as representative in democratic systems.²⁴

This is a global reality that does not coincide with the limited vision in which the notion of cultural hybridity that García Canclini tries to channel in theory is projected when cultural practice is much more comprehensive and complex.

Another critical reflection on the matter considers that:

²¹ For a critical dissection of postmodernity in the anthropological field, see véase Marvin Harris. «Antropología y postmodernismo», en *Catauro, revista cubana de antropología*, no. 0, La Habana, julio-diciembre, 1999: 44-62.

²² Italics mine, JG.

²³ Kokotovic, *Op. cit.* 294.

²⁴ See Vicenç Navarro, *Concentración de la riqueza*, Article published in the Spanish newspaper 'Público', 29/12/2011, en <http://www.vnavarro.org> (Consultado el 18 de enero de 2012).

[...] cultural hybridity also does not offer effective strategies to confront the neoliberal status quo. In García Canclini's work] hybridity is a mainly descriptive concept that lacks a normative dimension. García Canclini produces fascinating descriptions of processes of cultural hybridity but is unable to propose alternatives to the growing inequality of the societies where such cultural processes occur.²⁵

This makes the notion of hybridity insufficient to propose an alternative political project to neoliberalism and inevitably becomes complacent, submissive, and ultimately complicit.²⁶ Like neoliberal policies, it lambasts the instruments of the struggle against inequality, such as trade unions and political parties, as obsolete, and doubts the effectiveness of the new social movements,²⁷ but offers nothing of concrete interest. In this sense, its apparent neutrality is an open form of pro-neoliberal political militancy. On the contrary, there are other less pessimistic critical reflections on the historical and current role of social movements.²⁸

In his interpretation of the role of the mass media against the effectiveness of unions and political parties, García Canclini:

He argues that the transformation of the city and the colonization of the public sphere by the mass media have diminished the mobilizing capacity and therefore the importance of traditional forms of popular organization, such as unions and political parties. These organizations depended on public spaces and "micro-social structures of urbanity, the club, the café, the neighborhood society, the library, the political committee," where popular identities were constructed through interactions at the personal level, identities that formed the basis for political participation. Such popular institutions of urban life linked "immediate life with the global transformations sought in society and the State" so that "reading and sports, militancy and neighborhood sociability, were united in a utopian continuity with national political movements".²⁹

The argumentation with all this pessimistic charge is due to the structural transformation of the urban space and the manipulative effects of the mass media. This also obeys another of his main objectives: to erase identities, which according to him are built

²⁵ See John Beverley. «Estudios culturales y vocación política». *Revista de Crítica Cultural* 12, 1996: 52.

²⁶ The most forceful global project against unipolar neoliberalism is undoubtedly the Chinese initiative of the Belt and Road, with a broadly inclusive and participatory global scope. See Yang Zhen and Juan Jesús Guanche Pérez. *China-América Latina y el Caribe. Memoria, actualidad y perspectiva*, Madrid, 2018.

²⁷ Perhaps the best counterexample to the ideas expressed by García Canclini is the Movement Towards Socialism-Political Instrument for the Sovereignty of the Peoples (MAS-IPSP), led by the then Bolivian President Evo Morales, who has governed since 2006 and has turned that country into one of the fastest growing economies in the region and in full fight against inequality, until the coup d'état with the complicity of the OAS in 2019. See CEPALSTAT, Bases de Datos y Publicaciones Estadísticas. Comisión Económica para América Latina y el Caribe, en http://estadisticas.cepal.org/cepalstat/Perfil_Nacional_Social.html?pais=BOL&idioma=spanish (Consultado el 16 de noviembre de 2018).

²⁸ See Atilio A. Boron. —Compilador. *Nueva Hegemonía Mundial. Alternativas de cambio y movimientos sociales*. CLACSO, Buenos Aires, 2004; Atilio A. Boron y Gladys Lechini —Compiladores. *Política y movimientos sociales en un mundo hegemónico. Lecciones desde África, Asia y América Latina*. CLACSO, Buenos Aires, 2006.

²⁹ Kokotovic, Cit. *Culturas híbridas*: 266.

"less and less by local or national loyalties and more by participation in deterritorialized communities of consumers"³⁰ created by the mass media and very present in the author's mentality. This is the subject of another book, which in this logical direction is a continuation of the previous one: I am referring to *Consumers and Citizens*.

He considers that television has replaced the public spaces where personal interaction used to generate political participation, which has turned politics into a media spectacle, a simulacrum of popular participation and of abstentionism. This transformation in the experience of urban life has led, according to García Canclini, to an apparently irreversible decrease in the mobilizing capacity of unions and political parties. But there are also other, more acute interpretations, such as that of Ramonet,³¹ who explores historical and current issues of the media to manipulate mentalities so that naive or uncritical people perceive the world from what these instruments of transnational power say.

On the other hand, the issue is much more serious than what television or the possibility of having a cell phone can reach. This medium is not fully accessible in Latin America and that is why a World Bank article warns:

If you lived in a rural area and had to choose between buying a flat screen HD TV and having a bathroom with a toilet included, what would you choose? Think carefully because your health and that of your family may depend on the answer. Despite the economic advances of recent years, Latin America continues to face significant challenges to the development of the entire region. One of the most important is providing access to sanitation for the entire population. It is estimated that 120 million Latin Americans do not have a toilet in adequate conditions.³²

The commentary concludes by recalling that while mobile subscriptions exceed 6 billion worldwide, only 4.5 billion people have access to a clean toilet.

In view of the loss of the mobilizing capacity of parties and unions, García Canclini considers that social mobilization is fragmented through ecological, ethnic, feminist, human rights, women's, youth, and other movements, but he does not consider that many already existed, with or without parties and unions, if we include historical aspects in the analysis.

But García Canclini does not share such hopes and argues that the new social movements have shown themselves incapable of effecting structural changes: "These movements have been and are valuable as resistance", but "after thirty years of trying to build alternatives to parties and governments, in no country have they succeeded in

³⁰ See *Consumidores y ciudadanos...*: 24.

³¹ Another more profound and systematizing vision is provided by Ignacio Ramonet in *Propagandas silenciosas* (2001), where he analyzes the role of television and cinema as instruments of the hegemonic power of the United States of America.

³² See Banco Mundial «¿Una TV o un baño? El dilema en América Latina», en <https://consultarse.org/2015/03/27/una-tv-o-un-bano-el-dilema-en-america-latina/> (Consultado el 18 de noviembre de 2018).

erecting global projects and even less policies that restructure the state apparatus and the declining economies".³³

It is true that when the book *Consumidores y ciudadanos* appeared in 1995, it was not foreseen that any of the new social movements, such as the MAS-IPSP of Bolivia, which became a political party, could come to power in 2006 and remain in government until the 2019, precisely in the Latin American country with the longest record of coups d'état. Reality is always richer than reductionist generalizations or pessimistic visions. At the same time, due to the lack of political projection:

Many intellectuals overestimated the potential of the new social movements most of which had more modest goals and demanded answers to concrete problems from the state rather than trying to transform or replace it. García Canclini is right to point out the limitations of the new social movements, but the new political practices he proposes, *cultural reconversion and consumption*³⁴ as a form of exercising citizenship, seem no more capable of effecting structural change.³⁵

The criterion of reconversion, a term that sounds rather like religious confessionally, refers to the economic adaptation of factories, productive and technological processes carried out by hegemonic groups in the face of the neoliberal imperative, but it also occurs in disadvantaged sectors such as peasant migrants who adapt their knowledge to work and consume in the cities; They adapt their handicrafts to please potential urban buyers; the workers update their labor culture in the face of new productive technologies; the movements of the original peoples, even those called "indigenous", who place their social demands in international politics, sustain an ecological discourse and communicate it through radio and television.³⁶

Thus, for García Canclini, reconversion is one of the ways in which traditional cultures survive modernization. Instead of disappearing, traditional cultures "have developed by transforming themselves".³⁷

The conclusion is a truism if we consider the history of humanity and of culture in general, which has been characterized by the constant process of biological and cultural adaptation to the most dissimilar ecosystems, with multiple differences in the technological fields that coexist at very different levels of development, from hunter-gatherer and farming communities in the Amazon jungle that still paint their bodies and grow cassava for cassava, but use technologies that they did not invent, such as wristwatches, aluminum and nickel-steel containers, bicycles, machetes, steel knives, washing soap, among others;³⁸ to the megalopolises where sophisticated means of communication coexist (for a part of the

³³ Kokotovic, Cit. *Consumidores y ciudadanos*: 195.

³⁴ Italics mine, JG.

³⁵ Kokotovic, Op. cit. 296.

³⁶ See García Canclini. «Culturas híbridas y estrategias comunicacionales», 1996:3.

³⁷ See García Canclini. *Culturas híbridas*: 200.

³⁸ See the documentary *Imbé Gikegü. Fragancia de Pequí*, 36:25 mm, 2006, filmed in a Kuikuro community of Ipatsi, in Xingu, Matto Grosso, Brazil.

population) and another majority that struggles to work and subsist. Precisely because of the high degree of adaptive flexibility, although in the last two centuries the great attack has been against the ecological niche itself: the earth, we have managed to survive the most complex conditions.³⁹

This proposal of "cultural reconversion" is reduced more to a survival strategy than to a struggle for the equity of the popular sectors. By this type of reasoning, cultural reconversion is aimed at ensuring that neoliberalism enjoys good health; in other words, you adapt or perish:

García Canclini tends to exaggerate the role of hybridity in the abolition of the "hierarchies between historical periods." While I agree with his observation that the boundaries between times and spaces have blurred, I am not convinced that this is the case with hierarchies. The fact is that most traditional peoples and other subaltern groups continue to live under conditions of diminished opportunities. Cultural reconversion, that is, adapting cultural production to the demands of the market, is certainly preferable to lacking the resources necessary to ensure life and happiness, but it is difficult to accept that economic reasons are the solution to the problems of the production and consumption of cultural goods and the role of these processes in the construction of more democratic civil societies.⁴⁰

Therefore, the idea of cultural reconversion as a way to compete in the transnational capitalist economy, through the adaptation of cultural traditions, knowledge and practices to the logic of the market in the same conditions of subordination, are aimed at the annulment of cultural identities and their transformation into instruments at the mercy of the system that exploits them. The strategy of consuming to become citizens of global capitalism proposed by García Canclini does not solve the problem of inequality but rather eternalizes it and follows the rhyme of global neoliberalism. The reconversion proposal does not subject to criticism the difficult conditions in which the popular sectors find themselves to unleash creativity on all fronts. Thus:

Subordinating traditional cultures to the logic of the international market may be a means of survival, but it is at the same time a capitalist mechanism to produce profitable cultural differences. While reconversion does benefit the popular sectors, the hegemonic groups benefit more, and for that reason it is doubtful that it is an adequate strategy to change structural relations of inequality. It seems that García Canclini has become so resigned to the inevitability of capitalism that he can only imagine resistances that accept the logic of the system.⁴¹

This is in full articulation with the pessimistic conformism and the eternalization of neoliberalism, since "García Canclini's project [...] presupposes that the new stage of

³⁹ See in the written order Juan Luis Arsuaga and Ignacio Martínez. *La especie elegida: La larga marcha de la evolución humana*, Havana, 2014 and in the audiovisual *Planeta humano*. BBC television series, London, in eight chapters, 2011.

⁴⁰ See George Yúdice. «Postmodernism in the Periphery», in *South Atlantic Quarterly* 92, 3; 1993: 552.

⁴¹ Kokotovic, *Op. cit.* 298.

capitalism is, "beyond good or evil", simply the new condition of life, something inevitable, like having to drink water and eat".⁴² This crestfallen resignation is underlined in his proposal of consumption as a political practice.

While in *Hybrid Cultures* he addressed the consumption of objectual and symbolic goods, as well as the struggles for control of production identified as "cultural," in *Citizens and Consumers* he leaves production aside and concentrates on consumption, approached as a kind of privatized public sphere. Thus, he states:

Men and women perceive that many of the questions proper to citizens where do I belong and what rights does it give me, how can I inform myself, who represents my interests are answered more in the private consumption of goods and mass media than in the abstract rules of democracy or in collective participation in public spaces.⁴³

Here consumption appears as a form of political participation and not as a manipulated and alienating induction of the system's own propaganda harassment, which is nourished precisely by what transnational corporations invest in propaganda to guarantee their sales, which in turn conditions what is or is not disseminated in all mass media, what is said, how it is said and who says it. Now it turns out that consumption and how it is done are political acts. For García Canclini "To consume is to participate in a scenario of disputes over what society produces and the ways of using it".⁴⁴ With all that has been written and published on political and citizen participation, if García Canclini's proposal were not sarcasm, at least it has a whiff of complacency for consumption that has become delirious consumerism.

This point of view places consumption on a pedestal that replaces the obsolete traditional mechanisms of political participation and is the new scenario for exercising citizenship, so that politics and culture are subordinated to the logic of the market. Their adherence to global neoliberalism could not be clearer.

The new scenario presents threats and opportunities. García Canclini points out that the great majorities have minimal levels of consumption and therefore little participation in the new forms of citizenship. He considers that there are three levels of access to mass media: while the great majorities have access to television and radio, only a minority has cable television and video, and only a tiny elite uses satellite dishes and interactive media such as fax, e-mail, and the Internet. This inequality prevents the exercise of full and democratic citizenship through consumption, and for this reason, García Canclini proposes, "favoring generalized access to the last two modes of communication is a key condition for developing current democratic forms of citizenship [...]",⁴⁵ for which, unlike neoliberal policies, he assigns a fundamental role to the state.

⁴² See John Beverley. «Estudios culturales y vocación política», in *Revista de Crítica Cultural* 12, 1996: 52.

⁴³ Néstor García Canclini. *Ciudadanos y consumidores*, 1995: 13

⁴⁴ *Ibidem*: 44.

⁴⁵ *Ibidem*: 190.

Regarding the state, we were saying that the privatization season showed that private companies do not make the telephones, airlines, or cultural communications that our rulers handed over to them work better. This failure does not justify any restoration of the state as a guardian of telluric nationalism, nor as an efficient administrator, nor as an agent of populist donations.

The challenge is rather to revitalize the State as representative of the public interest, as arbiter or guarantor that the collective needs for information, recreation and innovation are not always subordinated to commercial profitability.⁴⁶

But what kind of state does this author want or propose, with a minimum of functions, only to ensure that consumers are better informed, or that they are better manipulated? García Canclini's proposal rushes into a political vacuum because he has discarded unions, parties, and new social movements as ineffective, leaving him no alternative but to turn to the neoliberal state to intervene in the market and guarantee access to symbolic and objectual goods, which departs from his transnational interests. It is thus left in a dead end and its proposals are extinguished in its own contradictions. For this reason:

García Canclini, in the end, remains essentially within the logic of the system instead of creating a space of opposition or stimulating the contradictions of the system. What is more, he transfers the agency of a popular and democratic subject to a specific new type of intellectual, whose tasks and goals are now defined by cultural studies and "theory" [...] If hybridity encompasses the market, consumer preferences and possessive individualism, then, despite Canclini's protestations that the purpose of his work is to make a contribution towards reformulating the project of the left, there is also a sense in which this work is compatible with globalization and neoliberal hegemony.⁴⁷

For all the above reasons, the theoretical proposal of cultural hybridity is not a valid conception to explain the growing inequality generated by global neoliberalism. However, García Canclini has contributed to the study of popular cultures in the conditions of dependent capitalism in Latin America, he has contributed descriptive reflections and specific analyses of specific processes of great interest, especially of the mass media, which break down when he tries to generalize them in an abrupt manner.

To better understand and explain these processes, it is necessary to revisit the scope and transcendence of the *transculturation* proposed by Fernando Ortiz. This conception provides an answer, due to its dialectical flexibility, to many processes of change taking place today.

The demonstrative argumentation he uses goes beyond the historical-cultural context of Cuba to connect in the categories of international anthropological knowledge and of social sciences in general. One of the main contents of his argumentation, when referring to the complex immigration processes that serve as genesis to the contemporary Cuban ethnos, is

⁴⁶ *Ibidem*: 190.

⁴⁷ Beverly, John. *Subalternity and Representation: Arguments in Cultural Theory*, 1999:129.

the striking compactation of intercultural relations between the level of development of the European senders of migration and that of the aboriginal receivers on this side of the Atlantic. In that sense, he points out that: "All the cultural scale that Europe experienced in more than four millennia, happened in Cuba in less than four centuries. What there was a climb up ramps and steps, here has been progress by leaps and bounds".⁴⁸ In this way he arrives at another key idea when he states. "In one day several ages were passed in Cuba; it would be said that thousands of culture-years, if such a metric were admissible for the chronology of peoples".⁴⁹

Today we know that it has been possible to calculate, compare and compact in ninety seconds millions of years, to establish the chronological relationship between the origin of the Earth with the origin of life and in it of human beings.⁵⁰ Of these ninety seconds, only the last one would correspond to the origin of hominids and only the last few seconds to the entire history of humanity. In this sense, the image drawn by Ortiz is valid to signify the scope of transculturation in its space-temporal and human dimensions. At the end of his argument, he also recognizes that "the concept of transculturation is cardinal and elementally indispensable to understand the history of Cuba and, for analogous reasons, that of all America in general".⁵¹

In its historical dimension, the clear opposition between *transculturation* vs. *acculturation* is part of the valuation that Fernando Ortiz contributes to the cultural dignity of each people, as opposed to diverse prejudiced and discriminatory conceptions that have weighed down anthro-pological studies up to our days.

As part of the application of his theoretical conception, in one of his works *El engaño de las razas* (*The deception of races*), where he makes a bold criticism of racist theories and practices, while defending culture as a substantial human quality, he writes: "American history cannot be understood without knowing the history of all the ethnic essences that have merged in this continent and without appreciating what has been the true result of their reciprocal transculturation".⁵²

All this is key to the defense of cultural identities, in the face of all attempts to disappear them, to the safeguarding of cultural diversity that has the same scope in humans as biological diversity, in the face of the passive complacency of global neoliberalism that also has its global alternatives, and in the face of the crestfallen pessimism of theorizing to align oneself with the mechanisms of world domination.

⁴⁸ Fernando Ortiz. «Del fenómeno social de la "transculturación" y de su importancia en Cuba», in *Contrapunteo cubano del tabaco y el azúcar*, Havana, 1983: 87.

⁴⁹ *Ibíd*em: 88.

⁵⁰ See *The History of the Earth in 90 Seconds*, about the work of musician John Boswell, creator of Symphony of Science, at <https://siliseed.com/curiosidades/la-historia-de-la-tierra-en-90-segundos/> (Accessed November 19, 2018).

⁵¹ *Op. cit.* 90.

⁵² *Op. cit.* 31-32.

Published in Spanish by *Temas. Cultura, ideología, sociedad*, no. 98, La Habana, abril-junio de 2019: 103-110 (ISSN: 0864-134X)